

Comparative Studies of Autoxidation of Ferrous Ions in Corn-starch Gel with those of the Haemoglobins in Human Red Blood Cells

BINAY KUMAR GHOSH

7705 Watson Street, Austin, Texas, 78757-1539, U.S.A.

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The observed increase in the relaxivity of Fe^{II} ions in its ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) complex solution over that in ferrous sulphate solution is rationalised. Spin-lattice (T_1) and spin-spin (T_2) relaxation times of haemoglobin (Hb) solutions are recorded. The extents of the respective decreases of the T_1 s and T_2 s in packed red blood cell (PRBC) samples during the autoxidations of their Hb-iron contents are compared with those of the Fe^{II} ions in corn-starch gel samples during the periods of the respective chemical changes. The continued decreases of both T_1 s and T_2 s in two samples of a freshly prepared corn-starch gel have been monitored for a shorter experimental period from the time of preparation of the gel.

At ≈ 13.2 MHz and 29° , the T_1 of water-protons¹ in a sample of deionised water was measured to be about 3 s (3000 ms). The T_2 of water-protons² of that sample, during the period of the reported experiments approximated 2 s (2000 ms).

Presence of paramagnetic metal ions, such as Fe^{III} in the experimental samples, decreased both the T_1 and the T_2 of the water-protons³ in each such sample. This shortening of the relaxation time is described as paramagnetic relaxation. Such enhancement of relaxation time due to Fe^{III} ions is greater than that for the Fe^{II} ions. At $T_1 = 460$ ms for example, this enhancement due to Fe^{III} ions was measured to be 24 times than that due to Fe^{II} ions. Even the EDTA complexes of the respective ions, in the corresponding solutions, shortened the relaxation times of those water-protons. The extent of such enhancement due to the Fe^{III} complex was also observed to be greater than that of

Fig. 1. Plots of T_1 vs time of $\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$ chemical change in : (O) PRBC sample at 27° , (\square) PRBC sample at 22° and (\bullet and \blacksquare) corn-starch gel samples at 22° .

Fig. 2. Plots of T_2 vs time of $\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$ chemical change in : (O) PRBC sample at 27° , (\square) PRBC sample at 22° and (\bullet and \blacksquare) corn-starch gel samples at 22° .

the Fe^{II} complex. At $T_2 = 175$ ms, the relaxivity of the Fe^{III} -EDTA complex solution was measured to be 3.3 times than that of the corresponding Fe^{II} -complex solution. The relaxivity of the Fe^{II} -EDTA complex solution with respect to the concentration of the Fe^{II} ions was, however, greater than the corresponding ferrous sulphate solution. At $T_2 = 175$ ms it was measured to be 1.27 times.

Biopolymers, like proteins and starch, also shorten the T_1 s and T_2 s of water-protons of the respective solutions. Thus, the T_1 of a freshly made corn-starch gel (6.1%, w/v) in dilute hydrochloric acid (pH = 1.9) was measured to be 1942 ms at ≈ 2.5 h after its preparation. Its T_2 was 177 ms at that time. When such a corn-starch gel contained Fe^{II} ions, both T_1 (\bullet and \blacksquare in Fig. 1) and T_2 (\bullet and \blacksquare in Fig. 2) got further shortened. In order to avoid confusion arising from possible differences⁴ in chemical and/or oxida-

tion states of the four Fe^{II} moieties^{5,6} in a Hb molecule, a deoxyhaemoglobin component will be denoted as HbFe^{II} , and an oxyhaemoglobin component as $\text{HbFe}^{\text{II}}\text{O}_2$. The cyclic sequence of oxygenation⁷ of HbFe^{II} within the lungs⁸ and deoxygenation^{7,9} in the capillaries^{9,10} gets terminated in the event of autoxidation¹¹ of the Fe^{II} moiety to Fe^{III} . In a normal young RBC, however, the dioxygen-molecule transport function is restored¹¹⁻¹⁴ after enzymic/biochemical reduction of the Fe^{III} moiety back to Fe^{II} . The purpose of this work was to rationalise the $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ autoxidation in the light of the *in vitro* experiments.

Results and Discussion

The curve (\square , Fig. 3) related the T_1 s of the experimental samples with the respective concentrations of Fe^{III} ions in the corresponding ferric chloride solutions. As the concentration of the Fe^{III} ions in the sample increased, the T_1 of the sample decreased. Similarly, the curve (\square , Fig. 4) illustrated the relations of the measured T_2 s with the respective concentrations of the Fe^{III} ions. The two curves (\circ , Figs. 3 and 4) relate respectively to T_1 s and T_2 s with the concentrations of the Fe^{II} in the experimental ferrous sulphate solutions. Although, the curve (Δ , Fig. 3) relates the T_1 s of different concentrations of solutions of a specimen of commercial human Hb, the corresponding iron contents are calculated amounts. The curve (Δ , Fig. 4) simi-

Fig. 3. Plots of T_1 vs concentration of iron corresponding to: (\square) Fe^{III} of ferric chloride solution, (\circ) Fe^{II} of ferrous sulphate solution and (Δ) calculated iron of haemoglobin solution.

larly relates the T_2 s of the experimental Hb solutions with those calculated iron contents. According to the manufacturer's label upto 75% of this product was methaemoglobin (metHb). In other words, as much as 75% of this iron happened to be Hb-complexed Fe^{III} ions. According to that label Fe^{II} ions of the $\text{HbFe}^{\text{II}}\text{O}_2$ complex correspond to the remaining amount of that calculated iron content.

Normal human venous blood contains negligible¹⁵ proportion of metHb. While 50.1% of its Hb content may cor-

respond to HbFe^{II} , 47.4% is stated to be $\text{HbFe}^{\text{II}}\text{O}_2$. Processing a fresh specimen of human blood from a normal donor, provided two PRBC samples. While their T_1 s were 557 and 566 ms, their T_2 s were 167 and 162 ms.

The curve (\square in Fig. 1) related the changes in T_1 s at $\approx 22^\circ$ with time in one of those PRBC samples. Such T_2 changes of this sample with time at the same temperature, were related in the curve (\square in Fig. 2). Similar changes of T_1 s and T_2 s with time at $\approx 27^\circ$ in the other PRBC sample

Fig. 4. Plots of T_2 vs concentration of iron corresponding to: (\square) Fe^{III} of ferric chloride solution, (\circ) Fe^{II} of ferrous sulphate and (Δ) calculated iron of haemoglobin solution.

corresponded to the respective curves (\circ in Figs. 1 and 2). The observed decreases in both of the relaxation times (\square, \circ in Figs. 1 and 2) during the described experimental periods corresponded primarily to the $\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$ chemical changes.

The respective T_1 and T_2 of a ferrous sulphate solution (Fe^{II} concentration: 13.44 mg/dl) were measured to be 721 and 595 ms. A corn-starch gel (6.1%, w/v) was prepared in it. The T_1 of a sample (pH = 2) after 2 h and 40 min of its preparation, was determined to be 620 ms. Its T_2 was 161 ms. Another sample was collected 1 h after this one. The respective T_1 and T_2 of that sample were 613 and 158 ms. Changes in their T_1 s (\bullet, \blacksquare in Fig. 1) and T_2 s (\bullet, \blacksquare in Fig. 2) with time at $\approx 22^\circ$ were compared with those of the two PRBC samples (\square, \circ in Figs. 1 and 2).

When the Fe^{II} ions were eliminated from such a corn-starch gel (6.1%, w/v; prepared in dilute HCl of pH 1.9), the T_1 -changes of two samples (\circ, \square in Fig. 5) during a much shorter experimental period, indicated of continued increase in the micellar regions. The observed changes in their respective T_2 s (\circ, \square in Fig. 6) during the same experimental period, indicated of the corresponding increases

in the proportion of 'hydration' water.

Considering d^2sp^3 hybridisation of the donated electrons to the Fe^{II} moiety in Fe^{II} EDTA. H_2O complex, 12 electrons (10 from EDTA and 2 from the oxygen atom of the H_2O molecule) are supposed to comprise the six octahedral orbitals. This Fe^{II} -moiety has also six $3d$ electrons. In order to rationalise the observed paramagnetic property of this *inner orbital*¹⁶ complex, the arrangement of those $3d$ -core electrons is supposed to be like that in a weak¹⁷ ligand field. The 'half-quenched' arrangement of Griffith¹⁸,

Fig. 5. Plots of T_1 vs time of two samples (O and □) of a freshly prepared corn-starch gel.

for example, has been reported¹⁹ in $S = 1$ ground state six-coordinated iron(II). The chemical change $Fe^{2+} \rightarrow Fe^{3+}$ corresponds to an electron loss from those $3d$ -core electrons. This electron transfer to a dioxygen molecule is very facile²⁰. The chemical change²¹ may be represented as

It is considered to be an outer-sphere process. However, the small size of the dioxygen molecule²² is stated to bridge the gap²² between cleanly outer-sphere and inner-sphere reactants.

Donations to the Fe^{II} moiety of a $HbFe^{II}O_2$ component in Hb

Such interaction is normally avoided in a $HbFe^{II}O_2$ due to structural safeguards. The Fe^{II} -moiety, for example, resides^{5,23} in a hydrophobic cavity. When the 'picket fence' becomes ineffective to bar the intrusion of an unbound, dioxygen molecule to reach the Fe^{II} moiety, electron transfer from the metal to that dioxygen molecule becomes possible. The lipophilic property of this⁵ small molecule appears to favour the intrusion. Thus, the competing process²⁴ produces $HbFe^{III}.H_2O$ *in vivo*.

As much as 3% Hb gets autoxidised in a normal human being daily. Restoration phenomena¹¹⁻¹⁴ maintain the level of metHb concentration below 1%. In case of the reported *in vitro* experiments (□, O in Figs. 1 and 2), the existing enzymes can not bring about the $Fe^{3+} \rightarrow Fe^{2+}$ chemical change due primarily to lack of ATP. As the $HbFe^{III}.H_2O$ continues to be formed, the proportion of metHb in both the samples, keeps on increasing. This accumulation of complexed iron(III) in each sample is indicated by the downward trend of the curve (□ or O in Figs. 1 and 2) with the passing of time during each experimental period. Many chemical paths²⁵ contribute to the phenomena. The steep downward slope of the curve (O in Figs. 1 and 2) between the interval from the eighth to the twentyfifth days is indicative of the fast $Fe^{2+} \rightarrow Fe^{3+}$ chemical change.

The reaction between an Fe^{II} ion with a dissolved dioxygen molecule in the experimental corn-starch gel sample, starts with the formation of a weak labile association²⁶,

where electron transfer within the complex has not occurred. That forms a transient intermediate with a Fe^{II} ion²⁷,

which in acid solution breaks down to produce hydrogen peroxide, as

This hydrogen peroxide now oxidises two Fe^{II} ions in the following sequence :

Due to the continuing chemical change in favour of Fe^{III} formation, successive T_1 s and T_2 s (●, ■ in Figs. 1 and 2) kept up to be shorter during the experimental period. The striking steep of the downward slope, particularly during the first 10 days of the experimental period (●, ■ in Fig. 2), was not only due to the fast chemical change that got magnified by a particularly large enhancement of paramagnetic relaxation but also the content of 'hydration' water and its continued increase in each of the two samples. The

proportion of 'hydration' water with respect to the 'bulk' water continues to increase in freshly made corn-starch gel (6.1%, w/v at pH 1.9) even 30 h after preparation. As a result both $T1$ (O, \square in Fig. 5) and $T2$ (O, \square in Fig. 6) continue to shorten during this period. Since any 'tumbling' motion of the macromolecules is restrained in the gel-state, the extent of entire $T2$ -shortening corresponds primarily to the restrictions in motions of the perturbed water molecules. Much of those restrictions happen to be the consequence of hydrogen bondings. In that outlook, the continued $T2$ -shortenings with time (O, \square in Fig. 6) is indicative of new hydrogen-bond formations.

The influence of 'hydration' water on $T2$ may be apparent by comparing the concentration curves (Δ in Figs. 3 and 4) of the commercial Hb. The superimposition of the Hb curve on the Fe^{II} ion one in Fig. 3 is coincidental. Their separation (Δ, O in Fig. 4) in the respective relations of $T2$ s with the corresponding concentrations of iron, is not. The influence of the content of 'hydration' water in the solutions of commercial Hb on the $T2$ s of those sample pushed the curve (Δ in Fig. 4) to the left of that (O in Fig. 4) due to Fe^{II} ions in ferrous sulphate solutions.

Fig. 6. Plots of $T2$ vs time of two samples (O and \square) of a freshly prepared corn-starch gel.

Experimental

$\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99%), $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (M.w. = 270.3), $\text{Na}_2\text{EDTA} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99%; F.w. = 372.2) were used. Powdered human haemoglobin was purchased from Sigma. ArgoR brand (Best Foods : CPC International Inc., U.S.A.) corn-starch was procured.

A Fisher Accumet 900 pH meter fitted with a calomel electrode was used. Fisher buffer concentrates for pHs 4 and 7 were diluted as directed to get the respective reference pH solutions. A Seimco micropulse magnetic resonance spectrometer (New Kensington) was used for $T1$ and $T2$ measurements. While the $T1$ determinations corresponded to Freeman-Hill saturation recovery methods^{28,29}, $T2$ measurements were according to Meiboom and Gill³⁰ modification of Carr-Purcell method³¹. These programs were developed specially for PRBC samples.

The experimental ferrous sulphate solutions were made in freshly boiled and rapidly cooled dilute sulphuric acid solutions. Disodium EDTA solutions were made in freshly boiled and rapidly cooled deionised water. In some of those solutions the pH was measured to be 4.55. The Fe^{II} EDTA complex solutions were made by adding large excesses, in terms of molar concentrations, of the EDTA solutions to the ferrous sulphate solutions. The pHs of the resulting solutions varied between 1.95 and 3.5. $T1$ and $T2$ measurements were done immediately after each preparation of the complex solution.

About 3.5 ml of freshly drawn venous blood from one normal adult human donor, was immediately mixed with 45 U.S.P. units of sodium heparin contained in a rubber stoppered blood collection tube. It was then centrifuged in a Fisher Centrifuc 228 centrifuge for 6 min. The separated plasma along with the buffy coat, which formed the top-layer of the cellular content, were removed and discarded. Allowing minimum exposure to air, the remaining part of the cellular layer corresponding to PRBC, was gently mixed with a Pasteur pipette to make it homogeneous with respect to the RBCs of different sizes, shapes and weights. Two 0.5-ml samples of this uniform mixture of PRBC were transferred in the respective clean nmr sample tubes (103×10.25 mm) enclosed with a rubber stopper. $T1$ and $T2$ of each of these fresh PRBC samples were determined at 29° within 6 h of the withdrawal of the specimen of blood.

A calculated amount of corn-starch was mixed with measured volume of dilute H_2SO_4 (pH 2), containing the required amount of Fe^{II} iron towards the making of a 6.1% (w/v) corn-starch gel. The mixture was magnetically stirred with a Spin-barR at room temperature until the corn-starch suspension was uniform. It was then heated under continuous magnetic stirring until the mixture just started to boil. As the last traces of the suspended corn-starch went into solution it was removed from the stirrer-hot-plate, when both heating and stirring stopped. A 0.5 ml of the sample was transferred in a nmr sample tube stoppered and allowed to cool (\bullet in Figs. 1 and 2). After 1 h another 0.5-ml sample was transferred in another nmr sample tube (\blacksquare in Figs. 1 and 2). A corn-starch gel (6.1%, w/v) without any Fe^{II} ion or any other paramagnetic metal ion, was similarly prepared in dilute HCl (pH 1.9). Two samples of this gel were investigated (O, \square in Figs. 5 and 6).

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